

NEWSLETTER 01: 24/03/25

FHERITALE

First update on FHERITALE activities

Introduction by project co-ordination

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As the FHERITALE project progresses into its second year, we look back on the work completed in the project so far, and the next steps we will take to achieve the objectives of the project. We welcome all with an interest in the impact artificial materials are having on our food, health, and the environment to read on and find out more about the project, and we are happy to engage with you to maximise the impact of this project going forward.

We are looking forward to seeing how the FHERITALE project impacts your work.

REPRESENTATIVES OF THE FHERITALE CONSORTIUM AND INVITED EXPERTS IN UTRECHT, OCTOBER 2024

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PROJECT BACKGROUND

The FHERITALE project brings together partners from across Europe with expertise spanning multiple areas relevant to research into the impact of artificial materials.

Exposure to artificial materials, either as a result of their intended use (e.g. food packaging) or at the end of their lifecycle (e.g. plastic wear) can have a profound impact on human health either directly, or through the food we eat, or the environment we live in.

The FHERITALE project seeks to provide the European research community with a comprehensive overview of technologies and services relevant to understanding this impact. These services are expected to span multiple scales and disciplines, including high-quality metrology, structural biology, microbiology, and ecotoxicology.

FHERITALE's objectives include analysing the current landscape of available services, also beyond its partnership, identifying gaps, and engaging with stakeholders in the research community.

Communication and Dissemination

In the first year of the FHERITALE project, we have worked to communicate the goals of the project to relevant communities through social media and our website, as well as through direct communication.

This January we hosted our first webinar, focussing on micro and nanoplastics, with a number of expert speakers from aligning EU funded projects and organisations. You can watch a recording of the webinar [here](#).

You can stay tuned for upcoming events, as well as progress towards our objectives via our social media pages, and dedicated pages on our website. You can also visit the [publications](#) page on our website, where we highlight impactful research on the impact of artificial materials on Food, Health, and the Environment

A CROSS-THEMATIC LANDSCAPE OF AVAILABLE SERVICES

A key output of the FHERITALE project is the development of a comprehensive cross-thematic landscape of services available to researchers working on the impact of artificial materials on food, health, and the environment.

Throughout 2024 research facilities across Europe belonging to multiple different Research Infrastructures were surveyed for their capacity to conduct research in these areas, with the results now available.

A brief summary of the services identified in the questionnaire circulated amongst research infrastructures is shown here. For a more detailed breakdown of these services, [please visit our website](#), where a more granular list of services, and the research infrastructures that can help provide access to them, are illustrated for your convenience. You can also navigate to the research infrastructure websites for further info on the availability of these services.

if you are a member of a European research infrastructure, and offer a service not yet included in our analysis, we want to hear from you so we can update this schematic!

Service Type	Number of available services in this category	Research Infrastructures offering this service
Physical/chemical characterisation of Microplastics or other Microparticles	37	● AnaEE-ERIC ● EIRENE-RI ● EMBRC-ERIC ● EuroBioImaging-ERIC ● Instruct-ERIC ● METROFOOD-RI ● MIRRI-ERIC ● ELIXIR
Physical/chemical characterisation of Nanoplastics or other Nanoparticles	31	● AnaEE-ERIC ● EIRENE-RI ● EMBRC-ERIC ● EuroBioImaging-ERIC ● Instruct-ERIC ● METROFOOD-RI ● MIRRI-ERIC ● ELIXIR
Physical/chemical characterisation of Micro/Nanoparticles based on origin: Artificial, Natural, or Engineered	20	● AnaEE-ERIC ● EIRENE-RI ● EMBRC-ERIC ● EuroBioImaging-ERIC ● Instruct-ERIC ● METROFOOD-RI ● MIRRI-ERIC ● ELIXIR
Structural characterisation of Microplastics + other microparticles	27	● AnaEE-ERIC ● EMBRC-ERIC ● EuroBioImaging-ERIC ● Instruct-ERIC ● ELIXIR
Structural characterisation of Nanoplastics + other Nanoparticles	22	● AnaEE-ERIC ● EMBRC-ERIC ● EuroBioImaging-ERIC ● Instruct-ERIC ● ELIXIR
Bioplastics (biodegradable vs bio-based)	17	● AnaEE-ERIC ● EIRENE-RI ● EMBRC-ERIC ● EuroBioImaging-ERIC ● METROFOOD-RI ● MIRRI-ERIC ● ELIXIR
Risk assessment of Micro/Nano particles	14	● EIRENE-RI ● METROFOOD-RI ● MIRRI-ERIC ● ELIXIR
Exposure assessment of Micro/Nano particles	18	● EIRENE-RI ● EMBRC-ERIC ● METROFOOD-RI ● MIRRI-ERIC ● ELIXIR
Toxicity of Micro/Nano particles	24	● EIRENE-RI ● EMBRC-ERIC ● EuroBioImaging-ERIC ● METROFOOD-RI ● MIRRI-ERIC ● ELIXIR
Biological activity of Micro/Nano particles	24	● EIRENE-RI ● EMBRC-ERIC ● EuroBioImaging-ERIC ● Instruct-ERIC ● METROFOOD-RI ● MIRRI-ERIC ● ELIXIR
Monitoring of Micro/Nano particles	20	● AnaEE-ERIC ● EIRENE-RI ● EMBRC-ERIC ● EuroBioImaging-ERIC ● Instruct-ERIC ● METROFOOD-RI ● MIRRI-ERIC ● ELIXIR

WHAT TO EXPECT NEXT?

The work we do in FHERITALE is highly interconnected, with the output of one task often the input of another. This year we will build on our service mapping activities to define key thematic priorities and identify gaps in the service offering, culminating with a workshop in Bucharest in Autumn 2025.

We are excited to keep you informed with our progress towards these objectives, and if you would like to get in touch with us please contact us via social media, or via email.

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Find out more on how work in FHERITALE fits together via our [website!](#)

